
Types of Code Switching Used by Parents on Instagram

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Abstract

Code-switching is a phenomenon that will always occur in the bilingual community. People will consciously do code-switching in their communication when they have the ability to speak two or more languages. It occurred not only in oral communication but also when they used written form communication on social media like Instagram. This study aimed to analyze the types of code-switching found in parents' comments on Instagram. This study used the qualitative descriptive method to create a clear and well-organized analysis of the data. The data itself was collected from *Parentalk.ID* Instagram comment section, from feeds posted in May until October 2021. In analyzing the data, the writer used the theory proposed by Romaine (1995) to identify the types of code-switching from the data source. The study concluded that the most type of code-switching used is intra-sentential switching considering the easy application because it usually occurs in form of words or phrases.

Keywords: *code-switching, speech function, Instagram, parents*

1. Introduction

Sociolinguistics concerns the relationship between language and society to get more understanding of language structure and its function in communication (Wardhaugh & Fuller, 2015). With the support of internet development, human communication is unlimited in this globalization era. This phenomenon triggers the increase in language spreading and connection, especially in English (Poggensee, 2016). In this case, English becomes an international language. In Indonesia itself, many people can speak more than one or even two languages, for instance, the local language, Indonesian, and foreign language (Lubis, Surya & Muka, 2017). People from the middle class also started to learn English and that makes English the most spoken foreign language in Indonesia.

People who can speak more than one language often switch between the languages they use and this phenomenon is called code-switching. Poplack (1980) defined code-switching as "the alternation of two languages within a single discourse, sentence, or constituent." Code-switching does not only occur in oral communication but also in writing. This is shown by the communication process done by many people on social media. In order to relay their thought, people often switch their language while writing through social media.

There are many types of social media used these days, like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. Instagram is one of the top three most used social media in Indonesia that many people choose to help their communication process (Nurhayati-Wolff, 2021). But nowadays, Instagram does not only used for communication purposes but also as a medium to learn and share information about many topics. People can discuss in the comment section and share their experiences related to certain things like parenting and child caring.

The increased awareness about the effect of parenting style on a child's growth and development triggers many emergences of Instagram accounts that posted about parenting and childcare tips. That is the reason why many parents use Instagram as a platform to get information about parenting and their child's growth and development and interact with other parents in the comment section. In this interaction, they often switch their language between Indonesian and English. Based on that phenomenon the writer is interested in conducting a study on the topic of code-switching from the parents' comments on parental topics on Instagram.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1 Code Switching

Code-switching is a phenomenon that involves the use of two languages or linguistic varieties in the same utterance or conversation. Some people believe code-switching is a creative form of bilinguals but on the other hand, it is also considered evidence of incapability two use two languages properly (Hoffman, 1991). Furthermore, Bokamba (1989) defined code-switching as, "the mixing words, phrases, and sentences from two distinct grammatical (sub) systems over sentence boundaries in the same speech event" (as cited in Hutami, 2017). It can be said code-switching is the result of the bilingual community.

2.1.1 Types of Code Switching

Romaine (1995) defined there are 3 types of code-switching, they are tag-switching, inter-sentential switching, and intra-sentential switching. Below is the definition of those types of code-switching.

2.1.1.1 Tag-Switching

Tag switching involves the addition of a tag from one language into an utterance that is otherwise entirely in other languages e.g. *you know, I mean*, etc. Tags are easily inserted in a speech at a point of monologue without breaking syntactic rules.

2.1.1.2 Inter-sentential Switching

According to Romaine 1995, inter-sentential code-switching 'involves a switch at a clause or sentence boundary, where each clause or sentence is in one language or another.' This type of code-switching involves movement from one to another language between sentences. Inter-

sentential code-switching also includes the situation when a switch occurs from a whole or more than one sentence produced entirely in one language.

2.1.1.3 Intra-sentential Switching

Intra-sentential code-switching occurs within a sentence or clause boundary. Sometimes it also includes mixing within a phrase or word boundaries. This type of code-switching may be avoided because it has a high syntactic risk.

3. Method

The data in this study were analyzed with the descriptive qualitative method. The data source is obtained from *Parentalk.ID* Instagram comment section. Some comments from the feeds posted from May to October 2021 are selected as the data. Those comments were chosen because they contained code-switching. The writer used the documentation method to collect the data. Meanwhile, to interpret the data the writer used formal and informal methods. The formal method is used for showing the percentage of the types of code-switching using table format, while the informal method is used to describe the types of code-switching using sentences.

4. Finding and Discussion

4.1 Finding

Table 4.1 The Frequency and the Occurrence Percentage of Types of Code Switching in *Parentalk.ID*

No	Types of Code Switching	Frequency	Percentage of Occurrence (%)
1	Tag-switching	1	16.7%
2	Inter-sentential Switching	2	33.3%
3	Intra-sentential Switching	3	50%
TOTAL		6	100%

Table 4.1 shows the occurrence of the types of code-switching from the data source. There are 6 data found from the data source. The most dominant data found was intra-sentential switching with 3 data or 50%, followed by inter-sentential switching with 2 data or 33.3%, and lastly, tag-switching with only 1 data or 16.7%. Intra-sentential switching was the most frequently occurred because it is simple and usually occurs with word or phrase form.

4.2 Discussion

Tag-switching

Data 1

"Dia juga suka ngublek-ngublek adonan, temenin bikin kue, so what?!"

(He also likes to mix dough, accompany me making cake, so what?!)

(Thebolski, *Parentalk.ID*, 29 July 2021)

In this data, the writer shared her opinion about her unpleasant reaction to her son who likes to accompany her in making the cake. She believed that cooking is not only for females but also can be done by males. At the end of the comment, the writer added a tag-phrase "so what?!" which makes this comment consisted of tag-switching. Moreover, the exclamation mark at the end of the phrase emphasizes that is tag-switching. For that reason, the data above consisted of tag-switching.

Inter-sentential Switching

Data 2

“*Tapi dikasihnya cewe, Alhamdulillah disyukur dan dinikmati.* Hope she would be my besties.”

(But we were given a girl. Thank God, we are grateful and enjoy it. Hope she would be my besties.)

(Vnibella21, *Parentalk.ID*, 29 July 2021)

From the comment above, the writer conveyed her grateful feeling for her pregnancy with a baby girl even though she wished for a boy before. She enjoyed the blessing she received and hope that her daughter would be her best friend. In the beginning of the comment, the writer wrote in Indonesian, "*Tapi dikasihnya cewe, Alhamdulillah disyukur dan dinikmati.*" Then continued with a new sentence in English, "Hope she would be my besties." From the position of the language switch, this comment contained inter-sentential switching because it switched between sentence boundaries. Therefore, the data above can be categorized as inter-sentential switching.

Data 3

“The wheels on the bus go round and round, round and round, round and round... *bacanya jangan sambil nyanyi ya*”

(The wheels on the bus go round and round, round and round, round and round... don't read it while singing)

(Lailasofaa, *Parentalk.ID*, 14 August 2021)

The writer of the comment above shared the lyrics of her child's favorite song and jokingly told the reader not to read it while singing. At first, the writer wrote the Wheels on The Bus song lyrics in English and continued the comment in Indonesian "*bacanya jangan sambil nyanyi ya.*" in a different sentence. It means the data contains inter-sentential switching because it combined two clauses each clause is in a different language, from English to Indonesian. Thus, this comment consisted of inter-sentential switching.

Intra-sentential Switching

Data 4

“This is real unconditional positive love, *mencintai tanpa syarat, aku pikir memang cuma bisa dilakuin anak kecil.*”

(This is real unconditional positive love, loving unconditionally, I think it only can be done by a child.)

(Yunisaam, *Parentalk.ID*, 10 September 2021)

In this data, the writer commented on a post related to the topic of how pure children's hearts are different from adults. The writer started the comment in English, "This is real unconditional positive love" and continued in Indonesian "*mencintai tanpa syarat, aku pikir memang cuma bisa dilakuin anak kecil.*" This can be categorized as intra-sentential switching. According to Romaine (1995), intra-sentential switching occurred when the language switch within the same sentence. Moreover, this comment consisted of intra-sentential switching

Data 5

“Rumah berasa arena perang kalo lagi on duty semua ayah, ibu, anak.”

(The house feels like a battlefield when all is on duty, everyone, father, mother, child.)

(Tiarmaharani, *Parentalk.ID*, 22 September 2021)

The writer, @Tiarmaharani shared her experience during the COVID-19 pandemic when working and school from home. She said her house feels like a battlefield when the parents work and the child study from home. In the beginning, the comment started in Indonesian, "Rumah berasa arena perang kalo lagi" then inserted with the English phrase 'on duty' and finished in Indonesian, "semua ayah, ibu, anak." From the data above, we can conclude that this comment can be categorized as intra-sentential switching because there is an insertion of an English phrase within the same sentence in Indonesian. Therefore, this comment contained intra-sentential switching.

Data 6

“Jajan terus dukung UMKM, less stress be happy”

(Always snacking support small local business, less stress be happy)

(Kikiaklatiri, *Parentalk.ID*, 17 August 2021)

In this data, the writer wrote her new habit that developed after the pandemic which is ordering snacks from small local businesses to reduce stress from staying at home for a long time. In writing the comment, @Kikiaklatiri started in Indonesian, "Jajan terus dukung UMKM," and finish the sentence in English, "less stress be happy." According to Romaine (1995), this comment included intra-sentential switching. This comment started in Indonesian and then suddenly switch to English but still in the same sentence. For that reason, this comment consisted of intra-sentential switching.

5. Conclusion

From the analysis of parents' comments from *Parentalk.ID* Instagram account, there are three types of code-switching found in the data source, such as tag-switching, inter-sentential switching, and intra-sentential switching. Based on the finding on Instagram, the highest occurrence of code-switching used by parents on Instagram was intra-sentential switching with an amount of 3 data or 50%. This is due to the easy application because it usually occurs in form of words or phrases.

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